

Occupational Hazards and Safety related to Radiation: A Review Study on Awareness of Healthcare Workers

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ABSTRACT

Aim of this study is to review the awareness level among healthcare workers regarding Occupational hazards and risks in health care sectors in different countries. This is an intensive literature review study. Search was done using google scholar, PubMed, Scopus and Science Direct engines, with key words like Radiation Safety, Radiation Awareness, Radiation Hazards, Healthcare Professionals, Radiology Staff, Doctors and Nurses. The Search was limited to articles written in English which were published from 2006 to 2021. Only original papers that described health care worker's knowledge on radiation hazards, safety and radiation risk in the hospitals, clinics and healthcare establishments were included. We excluded studies which did not include the healthcare professional awareness on radiation safety and those published before year 2006. A total of 528 articles were screened from initial review and only 23 papers meet our inclusion criteria, out of this 10 papers described doctor's knowledge, 6 of them described radiographers, and 6 of them described medical staffs and only 7 paper described nurse's knowledge. Most of the studies reported that level of knowledge was less than 50% among the healthcare workers. Base on the available articles we have found that awareness level among healthcare workers was very poor in the different countries.

Keywords: *Radiation Safety, Radiation Awareness, Radiation Hazards, Healthcare Workers, Radiology Staff, Doctor, Nurses*

1. Introduction

Radiation exposure from medical procedures is a threat to health affecting millions worldwide (Dehghani et al., 2014). Ionizing radiation has been increasingly used during the past decades for diagnosing and treating different medical conditions (Dianati et al., 2014). People are exposed to natural radiation sources as well as human-made sources on a daily basis. Natural radiation comes from many sources including more than 60 naturally-occurring radioactive materials found in soil, water and air. Radon, a naturally-occurring gas, emanates from rock and soil and is the main source of natural radiation. Every day, people inhale and ingest radionuclides from air, food and water. Today, many sources of radiation, such as X-ray machines, linear accelerators and radionuclides are used in clinical and research applications. Such beneficial uses may at times create potentially hazardous situations for personnel who work within the hospital. The use of ionizing radiation in medicine has led to major improvements in the diagnosis and treatment of human diseases. More than 3,600 million X-ray examinations are performed, 37 million nuclear medicine procedures are carried out, and 7.5 million radiotherapy treatments are given every year worldwide (Kaya et al., 2017). Some studies were conducted among the health care workers to evaluate knowledge level on radiation safety.

A study reported that nearly all nurses working in Nuclear Medicine Departments (NMDs) in Kuwait are not aware of the radiation protection and risks. This lack of awareness has serious implications on both patients and nurses (Alotaibi et al., 2012). Most of the doctors and intern doctors underestimated real radiation doses (Arslanoglu et al., 2007). The level of radiation dose and protection awareness amongst radiographers in the sampled Jordanian hospital is inadequate (Alhasan et al., 2016). In recent years, the use of X-ray and computed tomography (CT) scans has continually increased as a means of accurately diagnosing patients' condition to render the most appropriate treatment available. As a result, patients and hospital staff are repeatedly exposed to increasing doses of ionizing radiation in comparison to previous years (Partap et al., 2019).

Radiation has negative biological effects on living organisms, which may vary depending on the dose and the duration of exposure. Since the doses of x-rays used for diagnostic purposes are small, it is generally considered that health risks to individuals are also small. However, the growing number of people exposed to x-ray radiation makes low-level x-ray radiation dosing a more pressing concern (Yurt et al., 2014). In modern life the resistivity of radiation is impossible and the adverse effects of ionized radiation are known by majority. The international institutions which are authority on radiation and its practice fields are determined the minimum allowed dosage ranges for professionals who are working with radiation (Erkan et al., 2019). Although the adverse health effects of ionizing radiation such as cataract, skin erythema, and cancers among others, are known to vary according to dose and duration of exposure, it is assumed that there is actually no safe dose of ionizing radiation (Wosan et al., 2016). It is estimated that for every 100 mSv of radiation dose in an average person, the cancer death risk increases to 25.5% from a background risk of 25% (Zhou et al., 2007).

Therefore, using their knowledge of protection, radiographers can minimize absorption of radiation in patients, while maintaining the diagnostic value of the radiographic image (Fatahi et al., 2013).

2. Aim of the study:

To review the awareness level among healthcare workers about radiation risks in health care sector.

3. Material and Methods:

This is an intensive literature review study. We conducted review of published articles on radiation safety awareness among healthcare throughout the world. The research papers are from following countries Canada, Turkey, Australia, Kuwait, America, Ireland, Iran, Nigeria, Poland, Egypt, Norway, Trinidad, Finland & India. The literature searches were conducted using Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus and Science Direct engines using keywords like “Radiation Safety”, “Radiation Awareness”, “Radiation Hazards”, “Healthcare Workers”, “Radiology Staff”, “Doctors”, “Nurses” and were limited to articles written in English. The

search included the published articles during the period of 2006 to 2021. Total 528 research papers were searched with the help of keywords during the above mentioned period.

Figure 1 shows the strategy for search of articles.

Inclusion criteria: All the articles including healthcare staff including Nurses, doctors, Radiographers, paramedical staff, Students and interns working in hospitals.

Exclusion Criteria: Articles which did not meet the inclusion criteria, articles written in other language, articles did not mention about the awareness of healthcare professional, Industry other than healthcare.

Total Articles searched: 528 articles

No. of articles meet the inclusion criteria: 23

No. of Articles do not meet the inclusion criteria: 505

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram for search strategy

Table 1: List of selected articles from the different countries

S. No.	Title of paper	Study Design	Study Population	Study Sample	Year of Publication	Country	Knowledge Level	Reference
1	Radiation Safety Awareness amongst Staff and Patients in the Hospitals	Descriptive, cross-sectional study	Radiology staff, Medical physics staff, Nuclear engineering Staff nurse	173	2014	Iran	71.10%	Dehghani et al. (2014)
2	Intensive Care Nurses' Knowledge of Radiation Safety and Their Behaviors Towards Portable Radiological Examinations	cross-sectional descriptive study	Intensive care nurses	44	2014	Iran	84%	Dianati et al. (2014)
3	Radiation awareness among nurses in nuclear medicine departments	cross-sectional survey	Nurses	26	2011	Kuwait	Poor	Alotaibi et al. (2012)
4	Doctors' and intern doctors' knowledge about patients' ionizing radiation exposure doses during common radiological examinations	Descriptive	Doctors' and intern doctors	177	2007	Turkey	Poor	Arslanoglu et al. (2007)
5	Knowledge and practice of radiation safety among health professionals in Trinidad	Descriptive Study, Cross-sectional survey	Consultant, Registrar, House officer Radiographer Registered nurse, Nursing assistant	118	2019	Trinidad	46%	Partap et al. (2019)
6	Evaluation of Awareness on Radiation Protection and	Descriptive Study	Physicians, nurses, technicians and other staff	92	2014	Turkey	21.60%	Yurt et al. (2014)

	Knowledge About Radiological Examinations in Healthcare Professionals Who Use Ionized Radiation at Work							
7	The investigation of radiation safety awareness among healthcare workers in an education and research hospital	Descriptive Study	Healthcare personnel working with radiation source in operating room, endoscopy, radiology units	101	2019	Turkey	90%	Erkan et al. (2019)
8	Knowledge of Radiation Hazards, Radiation Protection Practices and Clinical Profile of Health Workers in a Teaching Hospital in Northern Nigeria	cross-sectional study	Radiology, Radiotherapy and Dentistry staff	110	2016	Nigeria	81.40%	Wosan et al. (2016)
9	The protection knowledge and performance of Radiographers in some hospitals of Ahvaz County	Descriptive and cross sectional study	Radiographers	71	2013	Iran	Poor	Fatahi et al. (2013)
10	A survey of awareness of radiation dose among health professionals in Northern Ireland	Descriptive Study	Consultants and junior doctors	500	2008	Ireland	poor	Soye et al. (2008)
11	Radiation Safety Knowledge and Practices Among Urology Residents and Fellows: Results of a Nationwide Survey	Descriptive Study Internet-based survey	Trainees	165	2012	America	53%	Friedman et al. (2012)
12	Radiation Safety Among Cardiology Fellows	Descriptive Study on-line survey	Cardiology Fellows	267	2010	America	70%	Kim et al. (2010)
13	Student and	Descriptive	Student and	340	2010	Australia	Poor	Zhou

	intern awareness of ionising radiation exposure from common diagnostic imaging procedures	Study	intern					et al. (2009)
14	Assessment of radiation dose awareness among pediatricians	Descriptive Study	Pediatricians	220	2006	Canada	35%	Thomas et al. (2006)
15	Assessment of Physicians' Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Radiation Safety at Suez Canal University Hospital, Egypt	Descriptive Study	Physicians	120	2015	Egypt	40%-60%	Abdellah et al. (2015)
16	Nurses' knowledge of radiation protection: A cross-sectional study	Descriptive Study	Nurses	252	2019	Finland	High	Hirvonen et al. (2019)
17	Awareness of Radiation Protection Safety and Hazards among Healthcare Workers and Paramedical Students	cross sectional study	Healthcare workers and Paramedical students	74	2021	India	63.50%	Indukuri et al. (2021)
18	Evaluation of Technical and Protective Functions; Radiology Department Staff of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences	Descriptive-analytical study	Radiographers	60	2020	Iran	96.70%	Tohidi et al. (2020)
19	Radiation safety knowledge and practices among Irish orthopaedic trainees	Descriptive Study, Internet-based survey	Orthopaedic Trainees	26	2013	Ireland	Low	Nugent et al. (2015)
20	Radiation Safety Awareness Among Medical Staff	Descriptive Study	Nurses, doctors, medical technicians, support staff	150	2014	Poland	78%	Szarmach et al. (2015)
21	Awareness and knowledge of	Descriptive Study, Online	Final year medical	99	2017	Norway	35.55%	Kada (2017)

	radiation dose and associated risks among final year medical students in Norway	questionnaire	students					
22	Radiation Safety Awareness among patients and Radiographers in three Hospitals in Port Harcourt	Descriptive Study	Radiographers	150	2013	Nigeria	58.70%	Kamara et al. (2013)
23	Attitude and awareness of general dental practitioners toward radiation hazards and safety	Descriptive Study	Dental Practitioners	300	2016	India	11.7%	Aravind et al. (2016)

4. Results

Table 1 presents selected published papers from the different countries. Total 22 articles were selected from 14 countries across the globe. One paper was selected from Canada; Assessment of radiation dose awareness among pediatricians. Two paper were selected from America; i) F, ii) Radiation Safety Among Cardiology Fellows. One paper was selected from Australia; Student and intern awareness of ionizing radiation exposure from common diagnostic imaging procedures. One paper was selected from Canada; Assessment of radiation dose awareness among pediatricians. One paper was selected from Egypt; Assessment of Physicians' Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Radiation Safety at Suez Canal University Hospital, Egypt. One paper was selected from Finland; Nurses' knowledge of radiation protection: A cross-sectional study.

Two paper was selected from India; Awareness of Radiation Protection Safety and Hazards among Healthcare Workers and Paramedical Students and Attitude and awareness of general dental practitioners toward radiation hazards and safety

Four paper were selected from Iran; i) The protection knowledge and performance of Radiographers in some hospitals of Ahvaz County ii) Radiation Safety Awareness amongst Staff and Patients in the Hospitals, iii) Intensive Care Nurses' Knowledge of Radiation Safety and Their Behaviors Towards Portable Radiological Examinations, iv) Evaluation of

Technical and Protective Functions; Radiology Department Staff of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences. Two paper were selected from Ireland; Radiation safety knowledge and practices among Irish orthopedic trainees, ii) A survey of awareness of radiation dose among health professionals in Northern Ireland. One paper was selected from Kuwait; Radiation awareness among nurses in nuclear medicine departments. Two paper were selected from Nigeria; i) Radiation Safety Awareness among patients and Radiographers in three Hospitals in Port Harcourt, ii) Knowledge of Radiation Hazards, Radiation Protection Practices and Clinical Profile of Health Workers in a Teaching Hospital in Northern Nigeria. One paper was selected from Norway; Awareness and knowledge of radiation dose and associated risks among final year medical students in Norway. One paper was selected from Poland; Radiation Safety Awareness Among Medical Staff. One paper was selected from Trinidad; Knowledge and practice of radiation safety among health professionals in Trinidad. Three paper were selected from Turkey; i) Doctors' and intern doctors' knowledge about patients' ionizing radiation exposure doses during common radiological examinations, ii) Evaluation of Awareness on Radiation Protection and Knowledge About Radiological Examinations in Healthcare Professionals Who Use Ionized Radiation at Work and iii) The investigation of radiation safety awareness among healthcare workers in an education and research hospital.

5. Discussion

505 articles out of 528 articles from different countries were excluded due to the fact they were not matching the desired requirements for the review. Out of the selected papers one paper from Turkey, two from Ireland, One from Australia, one from Kuwait, two from Iran and one from Finland shows no exact numerical value for awareness level about radiation safety. Out of the papers mentioned earlier only Finland shows high level of awareness among healthcare workers i.e. Nurses, rest were representing the low or poor level of awareness about radiation safety among healthcare workers. One of the limitation of this study was that the search is limited to English language only. Out of the selected papers from the 14 countries, the study from Iran, Ireland and Kuwait included small sample sizes of healthcare workers. All the studies include doctors, Nurses, radiographers, paramedical staff, Fellows, students and interns for assessment of awareness level about radiation safety.

All the studies show the awareness level of healthcare workers towards occupational radiation hazards and safety measures. Overall the awareness level was not so high that

suggest for incorporation of various skill enhancement methods like trainings, workshops, campaigns etc. These activities will reduce the mortality due to occupational hazards and will improve organizational productivity and enhance employee satisfaction.

6. Conclusion

It was found that Iran and Turkey study shows highest level of awareness about radiation safety among healthcare workers. Most of the studies reported that awareness level of healthcare workers is less than 50%. It is concluded that overall awareness level was low among healthcare workers. But it is very important to increase the awareness level about the radiation safety to minimize the occupational risk.

7. References

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